

New data on the distribution of ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) in Kenya

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Abstract

New data on the distribution of 12 species and subspecies of ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae), which belong to 9 genera, 6 tribes and 5 subfamilies (Anthiinae, Carabinae, Cindolinae, Dryptinae and Panagaeinae) in Kenya are reported.

Keywords

Carabidae, Anthiinae, Carabinae, Cindolinae, Dryptinae, Panagaeinae, distribution, Kenya

Introduction

During the period 2003-2006, the first author collected many different coleopteran insect species in Kenya, mainly Buprestidae (Curletti, Sakalian, 2007, 2009; Sakalian, Georgiev, 2013; Bílý, Sakalian., 2014), but also Cerambycidae (Sakalian, Georgiev, 2011) and Tenebrionoidea (Ferrer et al., 2016). Among the other coleopteran material, some taxa belonging to Carabidae family were established.

The family Carabidae numbers more than 40,000 species worldwide. The fauna of the best studied area in the Ethiopian zoogeographical region – South Africa includes over 1,400 species (Schoeman et al., 2018), but its actual number in this country, as well as that of the Ethiopian region as a whole, is undoubtedly great-

er due to the still insufficient knowledge about ground beetles in the tropics and subtropics. A part of the carabid samples were identified by Dr. Augusto Vigna-Taglianti.

This note reports new data on the distribution of 12 carabid taxa belonging to 9 genera, 6 tribes and 5 subfamilies in Kenya.

Materials and Methods

The ground beetles were collected by traditional entomological methods: hand collection on the ground and attracting to lamp light.

The current status, synonyms and combinations concerning Kenyan taxa are reported according to Lorenz (2005). The names of the subfamilies, tribes and species and subspecies are listed in alphabetical order.

The studied material is deposited in the Scientific Fund of Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research of Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Sofia, Bulgaria).

Results and Discussion

Subfamily Anthiinae Bonelli, 1813

Tribe Anthiini Bonelli, 1813

Anthia (Anthia) artemis Gerstaecker, 1884 (Fig. 1A)

Elementaita Lake, 00°28'31"S, 36°15'46"E, 1820 m, 14-15.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Anthia (Termophilum) hexastictum hexastigmum (Gerstaecker, 1866) (Fig. 1B)

Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 04-06.11.2005, 2 ex.; 27-28.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Chilanthia cavernosa (Gerstaecker, 1866)

Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 04-06.11.2005, 1 ex.; Kipepeo Farm near Malindi, 24.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Cypholoba chanleri (Linell, 1896)

Lower Tana River, Gamba Guest House, 25-27.10.2005, 2 ex.; 20-23.04.2006, 4 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Cypholoba cinereocincta alluaudi (Sternberg, 1907)

Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 04-06.11.2005, 2 ex.; 27-28.04.2006, 4 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Cypholoba sparthulata (Gerstaecker, 1866)

Lower Tana River, Gamba Guest House, 25-27.10.2005, 2 ex.; 20-23.04.2006, 1 ex.; Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 27-28.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Cypholoba tetrastigma tetrastigma (Chaudoir, 1848)

Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 27-28.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Figure 1. Ground beetles collected: A – *Anthia artemis*; B – *Anthia hexastictum hexastigmum*; C – *Triaenogenius gerstaeckeri*; D – *Calosoma planicolle*; E – *Megacephala regalis excelsa*; F – *Tefflus zebulianus transitionis*

Tribe Helliunini Hope, 1838

Triaenogenius (Triaenogenius) gerstaeckeri (Chaudoir, 1877) (Fig. 1C)

Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 04-06.11.2005, 2 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Subfamily Carabinae Latreille, 1802

Tribe Carabini Latreille, 1802

Calosoma (Ctenosta) planicolle Chaudoir, 1869 (Fig. 1D)

Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 27-28.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Subfamily Cindelinae Latreille, 1802

Tribe Megacephalini Laporte, 1834

Megacephala regalis excelsa Bates, 1874 (Fig. 1E)

Kipepeo Farm near Malindi, 24.04.2006, 2 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Subfamily Dryptinae Bonelli, 1810

Tribe Galeritini Leconte, 1853

Galerita (Galerita) angustipennis Gerstaecker, 1867

Lower Tana River, Gamba Guest House, 20-23.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

Subfamily Panagaeinae Bonelli, 1810

Tribe Panagaeini Bonelli, 1810

Tefflus (Tefflus) zebulianus transitionis Kolbe, 1903 (Fig. 1F)

Voi Wildlive Lodge, 600 m, 27-28.04.2006, 1 ex., V. Sakalian leg.

We consider that this short list is only a small contribution to a better understanding of the species diversity of the Kenyan Carabidae. We expect a lot of new data to be established to improve our knowledge on the very interesting fauna of this country.

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